

Cost-Effectiveness Analysis of Oseltamivir, Favipiravir, and Remdesivir in the Treatment of COVID-19 Patients in Indonesia

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Author Contributions

SS, RM, MAK, RR, AA and AAS contributed to the conception and design of the study, data analysis and interpretation, and revising the manuscript critically for intellectual content. SS, RM, and AA were involved in data collection and analysis,

drafting the manuscript, and revising it until the final approved version. All authors approved the final manuscript and accept full responsibility for the study.

Data Sharing Statement

The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article can be accessed through the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Ethical Approval

The study obtained ethical clearance from the Ethics Committee of Universitas Halu Oleo, Indonesia (registration number: 1127/UN29.20.1.2/PG/2024).

Disclosure

The authors declare that they have no competing interest in this work.

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Background: The selection of antiviral therapy for COVID-19 should consider both clinical efficacy and economic feasibility. Oseltamivir, Favipiravir, and Remdesivir are commonly administered antivirals with varying cost-effectiveness profiles. **Aims:** This study evaluates the cost-effectiveness of these three antiviral agents in treating COVID-19, based on improvements in Cycle Threshold (CT) values and oxygen saturation (SpO₂) levels. **Materials and Methods:** A retrospective, cross-sectional study was conducted at Bahteramas General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia. Of 2,108 COVID-19 patients, 337 met the inclusion criteria, with 88 patients having complete CT value data pre- and post-antiviral therapy. Cost-effectiveness was assessed by comparing total treatment costs with clinical outcomes, including length of hospital stay, CT value improvement, and SpO₂ recovery. Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratios (ICERs) were calculated for Favipiravir and Remdesivir relative to Oseltamivir. A one-way deterministic sensitivity analysis was performed to assess the impact of cost variations on cost-effectiveness outcomes. **Results:** The findings revealed that Favipiravir was associated with the shortest hospital stay, particularly in isolation rooms, compared to Remdesivir and Oseltamivir. Favipiravir also demonstrated the highest clinical effectiveness in improving patient outcomes (80%), followed by Oseltamivir (76.9%) and Remdesivir (66.7%). The highest treatment cost was associated with Remdesivir (US\$3,699.64), followed by Oseltamivir (US\$3,163.72), and Favipiravir (US\$3,149.84). Cost-effectiveness analysis indicated that Favipiravir had the most favorable cost-effectiveness profile, with an ICER of US\$3,870 per patient, compared to Remdesivir's ICER of US\$6,986. Sensitivity analysis identified treatment effectiveness as the most influential factor in reducing ICER values. **Conclusion:** This study underscores Favipiravir as the most cost-effective option for COVID-19 management, supporting its integration into standard treatment protocols grounded in clinical and economic evidence.

Keywords: Antiviral; COVID-19; ICER, pharmacoeconomics; treatment effectiveness

Introduction

COVID-19 is a highly contagious infectious disease caused by Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), which has escalated into a global pandemic with significant public health and healthcare system impacts worldwide [1]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the global number of COVID-19 cases rose drastically from 273 million cases with 5.3 million deaths in 2021 to 776,205,140 confirmed cases and 7,064,380 deaths by 2024 [2,3]. In Europe, approximately 36.8% of the population was reported to be infected with a mortality rate of 29.5%, making it the most severely affected region after South America in terms of death toll [4].

In Indonesia, the spread of COVID-19 also demonstrated a significant upward trend. As of November 24, 2022, the confirmed cases reached 6,627,538, with 159,524 deaths, while 6,403,551 patients were reported to have recovered [5]. At the regional level, Southeast Sulawesi, one of Indonesia's provinces, experienced a notable surge with 20,173 confirmed cases and 528 deaths as of December 2021 [6]. The pandemic has led to widespread health consequences and imposed a substantial financial burden on healthcare facilities [7]. Hospitals were required to mobilize additional resources, including isolation units, oxygen therapy, intensive care services, and antiviral agents as part of the COVID-19 treatment protocol [8].

With the increasing case burden, the demand for antiviral treatments that are both clinically effective and economically efficient has become a priority in COVID-19 management. The Indonesian government, through the Ministry of Health Decree No. HK.01.07/MENKES/4826/2021, implemented a maximum retail price policy for several drug categories used in the treatment of COVID-19, including antivirals such as Oseltamivir, Favipiravir, and Remdesivir. However, comprehensive pharmacoeconomic

evaluations of these antivirals during the pandemic have been limited, particularly in the Indonesian context. Such evaluations are crucial for optimizing treatment strategies. This study was designed to compare the cost-effectiveness of these antivirals based on their virologic outcomes, measured through Cycle Threshold (CT) values, and from a healthcare (hospital) cost perspective. Therefore, this study aims to assess the cost-effectiveness of Oseltamivir, Favipiravir, and Remdesivir in the treatment of COVID-19 using real-world data from Bahteramas General Hospital, one of the primary referral hospitals in Southeast Sulawesi Province, Indonesia. It is important to note that although Oseltamivir was initially included in the antiviral regimen and widely administered to COVID-19 patients in Indonesia, its use in this study was limited due to a change in national treatment guidelines in December 2020, which no longer recommended Oseltamivir for COVID-19 management [9].

The novelty of this study lies in integrating CT values as an additional marker of therapeutic effectiveness in pharmacoeconomic analysis. CT values reflect clinical improvement and provide a quantitative measure of viral load reduction, which has implications for lowering viral transmission potential [10]. However, using RT-PCR CT values as the primary outcome measure has certain limitations, particularly its inability to differentiate between viable viruses and non-infectious viral fragments, even in individuals who are no longer contagious [11]. To address this limitation, this study also includes peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO_2) levels as a complementary parameter to assess clinical improvement and therapeutic effectiveness. The methodological approach adopted in this research offers a new dimension to the pharmacoeconomic evaluation of COVID-19 antivirals. The findings of this study are expected to serve as a valuable reference for policymakers in developing more cost-effective treatment strategies and

supporting more efficient allocation of healthcare resources, both in the current pandemic setting and future infectious disease outbreaks.

Methods

This study employed a retrospective pharmacoeconomic evaluation with a cross-sectional design to assess the cost-effectiveness of antiviral therapies (Oseltamivir, Favipiravir, and Remdesivir) for treating COVID-19. The primary analysis was conducted descriptively using secondary data from electronic medical records and hospital billing systems at Bahteramas General Hospital, located in Southeast Sulawesi Province, Indonesia, covering the period from 2020 to 2023. Ethical clearance for this study was granted by the Ethics Committee of Universitas Halu Oleo, Indonesia (approval number: 1127/UN29.20.1.2/PG/2024).

The dataset comprised clinical information, antiviral regimens, direct medical costs, and patient outcomes, all sourced from retrospective records of patients who had received antiviral therapy. Of 2,108 confirmed COVID-19 patients, 337 met the inclusion criteria, with 88 patients having complete data on CT value and SpO₂ level before and after antiviral treatment.

Inclusion criteria encompassed patients with laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 via real-time polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR), those who were hospitalized at Bahteramas General Hospital, and individuals who received monotherapy with Oseltamivir, Favipiravir, or Remdesivir as part of their clinical management protocol. Disease severity was stratified based on CT values, per guidelines from the Indonesian Society for Clinical Microbiology: a CT value < 29 was classified as strongly positive, 30–37 as positive, and 38–40 as weakly positive [12]. Only patients with complete clinical and economic data (including cost of therapy and clinical outcomes) were included in the final analysis. Patients who were discharged against medical advice, had

a change in antiviral regimen during treatment, or received combination antiviral therapy were excluded.

The pharmacoeconomic analysis was conducted using a Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) framework. Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratios (ICERs) were calculated to compare the additional cost per unit of effectiveness gained for each antiviral agent. The ICER was estimated using the following formula:

$$\text{ICER} = \frac{(\text{Cost Antiviral B}) - (\text{Cost Antiviral A})}{(\text{Effectiveness Antiviral B}) - (\text{Effectiveness Antiviral A})} \quad (1)$$

Where:

Antiviral A : Oseltamivir

Antiviral B : Favipiravir or Remdesivir

Therapeutic effectiveness was assessed using two clinical outcome parameters: (1) the increase in Cycle Threshold (CT) value, interpreted as an indicator of reduced viral load, and (2) peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂) levels, evaluated according to standard reference values from the literature. In addition, the length of hospital stay (LOS) was analyzed as a proxy for the patient's clinical recovery. The cost data were analyzed from the healthcare provider (hospital) perspective, incorporating direct medical costs. These included the total cost of healthcare services per patient, covering expenditures related to inpatient accommodation, healthcare personnel, diagnostic testing, medical procedures, pharmaceutical services, and non-medical support services.

A one-way deterministic sensitivity analysis was conducted to identify variables that significantly impact cost and clinical outcome estimates [13]. In this analysis, risk ratios were varied by $\pm 25\%$ from the base-case values, while all other parameters were held constant [14]. The results of the one-way sensitivity analysis were visualized using a tornado diagram to illustrate the relative influence of each input variable on the estimated outcomes.

Result

Patient Characteristics

This study examined the demographic characteristics of respondents, including age, sex, occupation, comorbidities, disease severity, discharge status, and the type of antiviral therapy administered. A total of 88 patients who received antiviral treatment were included in the analysis, consisting of 13 patients treated with Oseltamivir, 45 with Favipiravir, and 30 with Remdesivir. Most patients were classified as having severe disease, indicated by a Cycle Threshold (CT) value of less than 29, representing 90.91% of the sample (Table 1).

As shown in Table 1, the distribution of COVID-19 infection was higher among male patients (61.36%) than among females (38.64%). Sex has been found to influence both the incidence and severity of viral infections. Evidence suggests men are more susceptible to COVID-19 infection due to behavioral, genetic, hormonal, and immunological differences (Zaher et al., 2023).

Patients aged 41–65 accounted for the highest proportion of COVID-19 cases (38.64%), followed by those aged 16–40 (36.36%). In addition, over half of the confirmed cases (54.54%) were among individuals in the economically productive age group who remained actively employed during the pandemic. Increased occupational mobility and frequent interactions in public settings likely contributed to their elevated risk of SARS-CoV-2 exposure (Cox-Ganser & Henneberger, 2021).

Length of Hospital Stay

The effectiveness of antiviral therapy is reflected in its impact on reducing the length of hospital stay (LOS) among patients. An analysis of LOS in COVID-19 patients revealed variations based on the type of antiviral used, particularly in isolation rooms (Table 2). The shortest average LOS was recorded in patients treated with Favipiravir

(9.43 days), followed by Remdesivir (10.29 days), while the longest LOS was observed in the Oseltamivir group (12.6 days). These findings indicate that Favipiravir may be more effective in promoting clinical improvement during the early phase of COVID-19 infection.

In contrast, in general treatment rooms, the highest average LOS was observed in the Remdesivir group (10.89 days), followed by Favipiravir (10.59 days), whereas Oseltamivir was associated with the shortest LOS (9.88 days). Overall, the mean LOS was 10.06 days in isolation rooms and 10.5 days in treatment rooms. These differences in hospitalization duration reflect the variability in antiviral treatment responses and the severity of illness among COVID-19 patients.

Cost and Effectiveness Parameters

To evaluate the therapeutic effectiveness of antiviral use in COVID-19 management, an analysis was conducted on several cost parameters, including accommodation cost, healthcare personnel cost, diagnostic examination cost, medical procedure cost, pharmaceutical services cost, nutritional services cost, and non-medical procedure cost. Accommodation costs in this study included expenses related to isolation rooms and inpatient care facilities. Pharmaceutical service costs encompassed expenditures for antiviral agents and supportive medications administered during treatment. In addition, non-medical procedural costs comprised services such as those provided by the Central Sterile Supply Department (CSSD), laundry, and other ancillary hospital support services. Based on the data presented in Table 3, the highest total treatment cost was associated with Remdesivir (US\$3,699.64), followed by Oseltamivir (US\$3,163.72) and Favipiravir (US\$3,149.84). Although the cost difference between Oseltamivir and Favipiravir is relatively minor (US\$13.80), Favipiravir emerged as the most cost-effective antiviral agent. In terms of effectiveness, Favipiravir demonstrated

the highest clinical improvement rate (80%), followed by Oseltamivir (76.9%) and Remdesivir (66.7%). Regarding viral load reduction, as measured by increased CT values, Favipiravir resulted in significantly higher CT elevations, outperforming both Remdesivir and Oseltamivir.

Specifically, treatment with Oseltamivir led to clinical improvement in 10 patients, characterized by transitions from strong positive to positive or positive to weak positive RT-PCR CT values. In comparison, 36 patients receiving Favipiravir demonstrated improvement from strong positive to positive or weak positive categories. For Remdesivir, 20 patients experienced similar improvements. Nevertheless, overall findings indicate that Favipiravir and Remdesivir were more effective in increasing CT values in COVID-19 patients than Oseltamivir.

Antiviral treatment effectiveness was assessed using peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂) as a clinical parameter. SpO₂ indicates oxygenation status, reflecting the efficiency of pulmonary gas exchange and systemic oxygen delivery [15]. The level of SpO₂ improvement was categorized into three clinical severity levels: mild (SpO₂ > 95%), moderate (SpO₂ ≥ 93%), and severe (SpO₂ < 93%). Among patients who received antiviral therapy, clinical improvement in SpO₂ was observed in 4 patients (30.7%) treated with Oseltamivir, 20 patients (44.4%) treated with Favipiravir, and 14 patients (46.6%) treated with Remdesivir. Analysis revealed that Favipiravir and Remdesivir were more effective in improving SpO₂ levels than Oseltamivir.

Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio

The Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER) analysis presented in Table 4 demonstrates that Favipiravir offers the most favorable economic profile, with an ICER of US\$3,870 per patient with clinical improvement, substantially lower than Remdesivir (US\$6,986). Favipiravir also yielded more cost-effective outcomes in terms of CT value

improvements. This result is further supported by the analysis of clinical effectiveness based on SpO₂ improvement, where Favipiravir achieved a lower ICER of US\$6,288. The combination of greater clinical efficacy and lower incremental cost highlights Favipiravir as a more optimal therapeutic option in the pharmacoeconomic management of COVID-19.

Sensitivity Analysis

A one-way deterministic sensitivity analysis was conducted to assess the robustness of the cost-effectiveness outcomes for antiviral therapies in patients with COVID-19. The results are presented as tornado diagrams, as illustrated in Figure 1. The one-way sensitivity analysis revealed that the ICER for Oseltamivir-Favipiravir (Figure 1A) ranged from US\$3,074.84 to US\$5,134.46, while the ICER for Oseltamivir-Remdesivir (Figure 1B) ranged from US\$5,561.50 to US\$9,269.16. The analysis identified that treatment effectiveness and accommodation costs were the most influential parameters impacting ICER variability. Accommodation costs emerged as the second most influential driver, affecting total costs of US\$3,074 to US\$4,626 for Favipiravir therapy and US\$5,808 to US\$8,095 for Remdesivir therapy. These findings underscore that therapeutic effectiveness is the most influential determinant of overall cost-effectiveness, whereby even marginal fluctuations in clinical efficacy can result in considerable shifts in total healthcare expenditures.

Regarding the effectiveness parameter, a 25% decrease in treatment effectiveness resulted in an increased ICER, whereas a 25% increase in effectiveness led to a reduced ICER. This trend suggests that higher treatment effectiveness enhances cost-effectiveness by lowering the incremental cost per additional clinical benefit. Conversely, increases in direct medical and non-medical expenses, including accommodation, medical procedures, pharmaceutical services, diagnostic tests, healthcare personnel, nutritional

services, and non-medical procedures, led to proportional increases in ICER values. A 25% reduction in these cost components resulted in a decreased ICER, highlighting the sensitivity of cost-effectiveness outcomes to variations in healthcare resource utilization and unit cost [16].

Discussion

This study involved 88 patients diagnosed with COVID-19 who received antiviral therapy. Among them, 45 patients were administered Favipiravir, 30 received Remdesivir, and 13 were treated with Oseltamivir. However, in December 2020, Indonesia's national clinical guidelines stated that Oseltamivir, which was initially utilized as part of the antiviral regimen for COVID-19 in Indonesia, is no longer recommended for the treatment of the disease [9]. This national decision aligns with international recommendations, which do not support using Oseltamivir for COVID-19 due to a lack of proven efficacy against SARS-CoV-2 [17].

Before intervention, the majority of patients (90.91%) exhibited high disease severity characterized by a substantial viral load, indicated by a cycle threshold (CT) value of <29 . Demographic analysis based on sex revealed that 61.36% of the patients were male and 38.64% were female. This aligns with existing evidence suggesting a heightened susceptibility of males to COVID-19 infection, potentially attributable to immunological differences, including higher ACE2 expression levels compared to females [18]. Furthermore, demographic clustering revealed that most patients belonged to the economically active and highly mobile population during the pandemic, underscoring the need for effective therapeutic interventions to mitigate productivity losses and the associated economic burden.

The comparison among antiviral agents indicates that Favipiravir is associated with a shorter hospital stay in isolation rooms, suggesting greater effectiveness in

managing early-phase COVID-19 infection. In contrast, Oseltamivir demonstrated a relatively shorter hospitalization duration in treatment rooms. However, the differences in length of stay across the three antiviral groups were relatively small, suggesting that the choice of antiviral therapy did not substantially influence the total duration of hospitalization. Favipiravir's superior performance in reducing LOS is attributable to its broad-spectrum antiviral mechanism, which targets SARS-CoV-2 replication by inhibiting RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp), a key enzyme in viral RNA synthesis. As a purine analogue, Favipiravir is phosphorylated into its active form (Favipiravir-RTP), which incorporates into viral RNA chains, resulting in premature termination or lethal mutagenesis (error catastrophe), thereby rapidly and significantly reducing viral load [19]. This rapid decline in viral burden correlates with earlier clinical improvement, as supported by Joshi et al., who reported that early administration of Favipiravir reduced fever duration and respiratory symptoms by 2–3 days [20].

In contrast, Oseltamivir, an antiviral agent that targets influenza neuraminidase, exhibits limited pharmacological relevance to SARS-CoV-2 molecular targets. Its non-specific mechanism fails to inhibit SARS-CoV-2 replication, resulting in delayed viral clearance and prolonged hospitalization [21]. Several studies corroborate these findings, reporting no significant benefit of Oseltamivir in reducing LOS or mortality among COVID-19 patients [22]. Although Remdesivir also targets viral RdRp, its clinical efficacy is highly dependent on the timing of administration during the active viral replication phase [23]. In patients with high viral loads (CT <29), delayed administration during the hyperinflammatory phase, dominated by host immune responses, substantially reduces its clinical benefit, as tissue damage at this stage is primarily driven by cytokine storms rather than active viral replication [24].

A comparative pharmacoeconomic analysis of Oseltamivir, Favipiravir, and Remdesivir in treating COVID-19 identified Favipiravir as the most cost-effective intervention. The highest total treatment cost was observed for Remdesivir (US\$3,699.64), followed by Oseltamivir (US\$3,163.72), and Favipiravir (US\$3,149.84). Clinically, Favipiravir demonstrated the highest effectiveness, with 80% of patients experiencing clinical improvement, compared to 76.9% with Oseltamivir and 66.7% with Remdesivir. These results position Favipiravir as a dominant therapeutic option in terms of cost-effectiveness, achieving lower treatment costs and greater clinical effectiveness, as reflected by shorter LOS and improved CT values.

These findings are consistent with previous studies highlighting the pharmacoeconomic advantages of Favipiravir over Remdesivir. In Indonesia, Favipiravir was reported to have a lower Average Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ACER) and Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (CER) than Remdesivir for both inpatient and outpatient treatment settings [25]. Similarly, a study in Saudi Arabia found that Favipiravir was associated with a higher probability of discharging patients alive and lower daily hospitalization costs [26]. Clinical evidence also supports the favorable profile of Favipiravir, with significantly faster clinical cure times [27], and higher rates of clinical improvement at 14 days and virological clearance at 28 days. However, no significant differences were observed in mortality or ICU admission [28].

Pharmacologically, both Favipiravir and Remdesivir are broad-spectrum RNA polymerase inhibitors repurposed for COVID-19 therapy [29]. Despite their shared mechanism of action, they differ in safety profiles. Remdesivir has been associated with a higher incidence of adverse effects, including elevated alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels and drug-induced liver injury, compared to Favipiravir [30,31]. Moreover,

Favipiravir tends to be more beneficial in mild to moderate COVID-19 cases, whereas Remdesivir is typically reserved for severe cases [31].

Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER) analysis further confirmed Favipiravir's pharmacoeconomic advantage over Oseltamivir, with the lowest ICER for clinical improvement at US\$3,870. In comparison, Remdesivir-Oseltamivir yielded an ICER of US\$6,986. Notably, considering the average hospitalization cost for COVID-19 in Indonesia ranges from US\$4,613 to US\$6,151 [32], these findings reinforce Favipiravir's economic value in optimizing healthcare resource allocation. Regarding improvement in oxygen saturation (SpO₂), Favipiravir yielded a lower ICER (US\$6,288) than Remdesivir. Sensitivity analyses (Figures 1A and 1B) demonstrated that increasing therapeutic efficacy by 25% resulted in a corresponding decrease in ICERs for both Favipiravir and Remdesivir. Furthermore, reductions in accommodation, procedural, pharmaceutical, diagnostic, personnel, nutritional, and non-medical costs by 25% also led to lower ICER values, underscoring the influence of direct and indirect costs on antiviral cost-effectiveness.

This study affirms Favipiravir as the most cost-effective intervention among the antivirals evaluated, with a favorable cost-minimization profile. It offers an efficient strategy for healthcare resource allocation in the management of COVID-19. A notable novelty of this research lies in integrating CT values as an objective proxy for antiviral efficacy and SpO₂ parameters, factors seldom incorporated in prior pharmacoeconomic evaluations of COVID-19 antivirals. Nevertheless, this study has limitations, including the absence of a comprehensive budget impact analysis (BIA) and lack of evaluation of quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), which restricts conclusions regarding long-term economic benefits and patient quality of life. Additionally, the analysis does not fully account for interindividual variability in treatment response, which genetic

polymorphisms and comorbidities may influence. In addition, the data utilized in this study were derived from a single institutional setting. However, Bahteramas General Hospital is the main referral hospital for COVID-19 in Southeast Sulawesi, and the clinical team adheres strictly to national COVID-19 treatment protocols established by the Government of Indonesia. Therefore, the findings from this study are still considered representative of the region's treatment patterns and healthcare conditions.

Based on these findings, the study recommends the prioritization of Favipiravir as a first-line therapeutic option for COVID-19, particularly in resource-limited healthcare settings with high hospital burden. Moreover, these pharmaco-economic insights may serve as a valuable foundation for policymakers in adopting value-based pricing strategies for antiviral procurement, thereby enhancing health system sustainability and pandemic preparedness for future infectious disease threats.

Conclusion

Favipiravir has proven to be the most cost-effective antiviral for treating COVID-19, demonstrating superior clinical outcomes, shorter length of hospital stay, and more favorable ICER values than Remdesivir and Oseltamivir. This highlights Favipiravir as a more economically viable option, particularly in resource-limited settings. Sensitivity analysis indicates that increasing the effectiveness of the therapy could further reduce the ICER of the antiviral. These findings provide valuable insights for policymakers and healthcare providers in selecting the optimal antiviral treatment to enhance clinical benefits while maintaining financial sustainability in the management of COVID-19. Further comprehensive research is needed to assess the long-term economic impact and explore the potential integration of Favipiravir into standard treatment protocols, based on both clinical and economic evidence, particularly in COVID-19.

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Tables

Table 1. Patient Characteristics

Characteristics	Total (n=88)	Oseltamivir (n=13)	Favipiravir (n=45)	Remdesivir (n=30)
Sex				
Male	54 (61,36%)	10 (11,36%)	23 (26,14%)	21 (23,86%)
Female	34 (38,64%)	3 (3,41%)	22 (25,00%)	9 (10,23%)
Age				
<15 years	2 (2,27%)	2 (2,27%)	0 (0,00%)	0 (0,00%)
16-40 years	32 (36,36%)	6 (6,82%)	19 (21,59%)	7 (7,95%)
41-65 years	34 (38,64)	4 (4,55%)	19 (21,59%)	11 (12,50%)
>65 years	20 (22,73%)	1 (1,14%)	7 (7,95%)	12 (13,64%)
Occupation				
Student	12 (13,64%)	5 (5,68%)	6 (6,82%)	1 (1,14%)
Employed	48 (54,54%)	7 (7,95%)	24 (27,27%)	17 (19,32%)
Unemployed	28 (31,82%)	1 (1,14%)	15 (17,05%)	12 (13,64%)
Comorbidities				
With Comorbidities	41 (46,59%)	5 (5,68%)	19 (21,59%)	17 (19,32%)
Without Comorbidities	47 (53,41%)	8 (9,09%)	26 (29,55%)	13 (14,77%)
Disease Severity				
Pre-Intervention				
Weak Positive	0 (0,00%)	0 (0,00%)	0 (0,00%)	0 (0,00%)
Positive	8 (9,09%)	1 (1,14%)	3 (3,41%)	4 (4,55%)
Strong Positive	80 (90,91%)	12 (13,64%)	42 (47,73%)	26 (29,55%)
Post-Intervention				
Weak Positive	4 (4,55%)	2 (2,27%)	1 (1,14%)	1 (1,14%)
Positive	65 (73,86%)	8 (9,09%)	36 (40,91%)	21 (23,86%)
Strong Positive	19 (21,59%)	3 (3,41%)	8 (9,09%)	8 (9,09%)
Discharge Status				
Discharged with Physician Approval	84 (95,45%)	13 (14,77%)	44 (50,00%)	27 (30,68%)
Deceased	4 (4,55%)	0 (0,00%)	1 (1,14%)	3 (3,41%)

Table 2. Length of Hospital Stay for COVID-19 Patients

Length of stay (88)	Oseltamivir (13)	Favipiravir (45)	Remdesivir (30)	Average
Isolation Room	12.6 day	9.43 day	10.29 day	10.06 day
Treatment Room	9.88 day	10.59 day	10.89 day	10.5 day

Table 3. Cost and Effectiveness Parameters

Cost Parameters				
Components	Oseltamivir (13)	Favipiravir (45)	Remdesivir (30)	Average
Accommodation	2,617.77	2,558.52	2,666.66	2,614.32
Isolation Room	2,423.82	2,456.35	2,587.92	2,489.36
Treatment Room	193.95	102.17	78.74	124.95
Healthcare Costs	99.03	72.68	108.03	93.25
Doctor's Visit	19.24	17.31	25.47	20.67
Specialist Consultation	37.77	22.5	48.65	36.31
Nursing Care	42.01	32.87	33.91	36.27
Examinations	42.09	63.03	75.59	60.24
Electrocardiogram	1.97	1.05	1.94	1.65
Endoscopy	0.77	0.21	0.33	0.43
Laboratory	33.76	52.61	57.7	48.02
Radiology	5.59	9.16	15.63	10.13
Medical Procedures	226.67	257.19	406.45	296.77
Medical Actions	19.27	13.23	0	10.83
Surgical Actions	28.3	33.06	47.16	36.17
Blood Transfusion	3.41	10.34	8.86	7.53
Medical Gases	175.7	200.57	350.43	242.23
Pharmacy Services	117.16	155.46	401.89	224.84
Nutritional Services	57.17	39.27	37.54	44.66
Non-Medical Procedures	3.83	3.69	3.48	3.67
Central Sterile Supply Department	0	0.18	0	0.06
Laundry	0.44	0.35	0.29	0.36
Other Services	3.4	3.16	3.18	3.25
Total Cost	3,163.72	3,149.83	3,699.64	3,338
Effectiveness Parameters				
Number of Patients Showing Clinical Improvement Based on CT Value	10	36	20	22
Number of Patients Showing Clinical Improvement Based on SpO ₂ Level	4	20	14	12.67

*1 US\$ = IDR 16,255 (As of January 15, 2025)

Table 4. Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio of Favipiravir and Remdesivir

Compared to Oseltamivir

Categories	ICER Favipiravir	ICER Remdesivir
Number of patients showing clinical improvement based on CT value category	US\$3,870	US\$6,986
Number of patients showing clinical improvement based on SPO ₂ levels	US\$6,288	US\$6,986

*1 US\$ = IDR 16,255 (As of January 15, 2025)

Figure

Figure 1. Tornado diagram of One-way sensitivity analysis of (A) Oseltamivir-Favipiravir and (B) Oseltamivir-Remdesivir. An orange bar represents the effect on the ICER of increasing a parameter value (+25%) from its reference value, while a blue bar represents the effect of reducing a parameter value (-25%).

* Number of patients with improved clinical condition